

Characterization of the solubilization of Indian rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100 as a function of mineral elements

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The present study was taken into consideration to examine the effect of different macro and micro mineral elements on solubilization of Indian rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100. In this context, the effect of several mineral elements were examined (KCl, KH₂PO₄, CaCO₃, FeSO₄·7H₂O, ZnSO₄·7H₂O, CuSO₄·5H₂O, MnSO₄·H₂O, NiSO₄·6H₂O, CoCl₂·6H₂O, (NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄ and NH₄VO₃). KCl and KH₂PO₄ exhibited positive effect on solubilization of phosphate from rock phosphate ore at concentrations ranging from 0.10 to 0.03%, but calcium ion had adverse effect on solubilization of phosphate. It has been observed that among the micro elements studied, Fe²⁺, 20 µg/ml showed positive effect on solubilization of phosphate from rock phosphate ore. Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Mo⁶⁺ had no effect on phosphorus solubilization but Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ had adverse effect on phosphate solubilization from rock phosphate ore by *Aspergillus niger* AB100. In the present study, after optimization of different macro and micro mineral elements in the synthetic broth, solubilization of phosphate was increased significantly ($p < 0.001$) from 35.95 to 65.05%. Alteration of final pH in the broth also exhibited significant ($p < 0.05$) alteration towards acidity. Dry cell weight also increased significantly ($p < 0.001$) from 0.9 to 3.5 mg/ml. Thus, optimization of different mineral elements led to overall improvement in the solubilization of rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100.

Keywords: Solubilization, mineral, *Aspergillus niger*, phosphate, optimization.

Introduction

Most of the essential plant nutrients, including phosphorus, remain in insoluble form in soil. A large portion of inorganic phosphate applied to soil as fertilizer is rapidly immobilized soon after application and becomes unavailable to plant^{1,2}. Applying phosphate solubilizing microbes to soil as biofertilizer may alter this problem by solubilizing those immobilized products. Application of phosphate rocks, if solubilized by microbes, may help to increase the phosphate level of soil. Large rock phosphate deposits (estimated up to 140 million tons) are distributed in different parts of India³. Those deposits can be of organic importance, because of their significant phosphorous content. Effective phosphate solubilizing microorganisms can be used to release the bound phosphates, the process being accompanied by extracellular organic acids or hydrolytic enzymes⁴. The wide distribution of acid phosphates in *Aspergilli* perhaps accounts for the dephosphorylation of the rock phosphate added to the soil⁵.

Microbes utilize carbon sources and secrete organic acids⁶. Production of organic acids depends on the growth and metabolic activities of the organisms. Nutrients play an important role in this regard. Besides carbon and nitrogen, macro and micro elements play pivotal roles for growth and metabolic activities of *Aspergillus niger*. Therefore, sufficient growth and metabolism may enhance acid production which may increase solubilization of phosphate from rock phosphate ore.

Abd-Alla (1994) tested the potency *Rhizobium* and *Bradyrhizobium* for the solubilization of rock phosphate⁷. Chung *et al.* (2005) isolated phosphate solubilizing bacteria from rhizosphere of crop plants of Korea⁸. Bojinova *et al.* (2008) examined Solubilization of Morocco phosphorite by *Aspergillus niger*⁹. Mendes *et al.* (2015) optimized rock phosphate solubilization by *Aspergillus niger*¹⁰. Sane and Mehta (2015) isolated *Pennisetum glaucum* and evaluated their potency in the solubilization of rock phosphate¹¹. Jain and Sharma (2017) examined the potency of the two differ-

ent isolated fungi to dissolve hardly soluble phosphates in solutions¹².

This study presents the effect of various macro and micro elements on solubilization of phosphorus from rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100.

Materials and methods

Rock phosphate ore: Samples of rock phosphate ore were collected from Rajasthan State Mines and Mineral Ltd., Udaipur, Rajasthan. These were crushed in a ball mill and made into fine granules. Then it was passed through a sieve and 200 mesh size particles were collected.

Microorganism: Strains of *Aspergillus niger* were collected from composed soils of North Bengal. The mutant strain *Aspergillus niger* AB100 which was developed by treatment with mutagens such as Ethyl methane sulphate (EMS) and gamma rays, used in this investigation¹³.

Medium and culture conditions: The mutant *Aspergillus niger* AB100 was maintained in a malt and yeast extract agar medium. The spores were harvested; suspensions were prepared in 10 ml sterile distilled water and standardized at a concentration of 12×10^6 spores/ml of spore suspension. This was diluted to 5% (v/v) and was used as inoculum. Surface culture fermentation was carried out using 250 ml Erlenmeyer conical flasks with 160 ml fermentation medium at pH 4.0 for 8 days at 28°C with 0.1% rock phosphate ore of 200 mesh sizes. The fermentation medium used for solubilization experiments consisted of NaNO₃, 0.4%; KCl, 0.05%; K₂HPO₄, 0.1% and yeast extract, 0.01%. It was sterilized at 121°C for 15 min at 15 lbs pressure using autoclave. The standard concentration stock solution of glucose was sterilized separately and a calculated volume of it was added aseptically so that the final concentration was 4.0% in the medium¹⁴.

Addition of trace elements in the medium: Initially the fermentation medium did not contain any trace element to be investigated. The impurities present in the inorganic salts were further purified by the method as described by Majumder and Bose⁸. The solution of all trace elements prepared in triple glass distilled water, sterilized at 15 lbs pressure for 15 min and added separately to the medium to attain the required concentration¹⁵.

Determination of phosphate: Soluble phosphorus was determined titrimetrically by taking a fixed volume of the fil-

trate and precipitating with ammonium molybdate, 10% and dissolving it in (N/10) NaOH and titrating it with (N/10) HCl using phenolphthalein as indicator. From the volume of alkali consumed percentage P₂O₅ can be calculated¹⁶.

1 ml (N) NaOH \equiv 0.003087 g P₂O₅ \equiv 0.00139 g of phosphorus.

Estimation of dry cell weight: Growth of the organism was determined by measuring the dry cell weight of the mycelial mass. This was separated from the fermentation medium by centrifugation at 10,000 rpm for 10 min, washed twice with distilled water and dried to constant weight at 80°C for 24 h. Growth was expressed as mg/ml¹⁷.

Statistical analysis: All data were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n=6. The data were analyzed by One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), followed by Dunett's post hoc multiple comparison test using a software Prism 4.0 (Graph pad Ind, USA). A 'p' value less than 0.05 was considered as significant and less than 0.001 as a highly significant¹⁸.

Results and discussion

Effect of macro elements:

Table 1 showed that maximum solubilization of phosphate occurred at a KCl concentration of 70 μ g/ml. Lower concentrations did not support phosphate solubilization as evident from slight pH change. Moreover, with greater potassium applied, the growth of the organism was more which indicated that as growth increased, phosphate solubilization decreased with fungal uptake of the released phosphate for the growth. Phosphorus was added to the medium as KH₂PO₄ at concentrations of 20 to 120 μ g/ml. It was observed that, maximum phosphate solubilization took place at a concentration of 50 μ g/ml (Table 1). Utilization of phosphorus and the alteration of pH of the medium maximally observed towards the acidic side with a concentration of 50 μ g/ml KH₂PO₄ in the present study. Besides, being a component in aiding fungal growth and acted as a useful buffer added to the medium, it also exerted a controlling influence over the pH changes in the medium caused by fungal growth and metabolism. The role of calcium in fungal nutrition has been well documented¹⁹. Calcium often influences in an antagonistic manner against certain toxic monovalent cations like hydrogen, sodium, potassium, etc. It is evident from Table 1 that, calcium carbonate supported the growth of the fungus but did not support the phosphate solubilization. This was

Table 1. Effects of macro elements on solubilization of phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100 (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n=6)

Macro mineral elements	Concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Final pH	Cellular growth (mg/ml)	Solubilization of phosphate (%)
KCl	00	5.2 \pm 0.683	0.9 \pm 0.492	48.6 \pm 0.661
	40	4.8 \pm 0.713	1.5 \pm 0.662	50.0 \pm 0.618
	50	4.3 \pm 0.668	1.6 \pm 0.811	51.3 \pm 0.498
	70	4.1 \pm 0.592	2.0 \pm 0.613	53.3 \pm 0.813
	100	4.2 \pm 0.613	1.8 \pm 0.832	51.2 \pm 0.613
	120	4.8 \pm 0.662	1.7 \pm 0.661	50.8 \pm 0.883
	150	5.1 \pm 0.813	1.5 \pm 0.682	48.6 \pm 0.713
	KH ₂ PO ₄	00	4.1 \pm 0.681	2.0 \pm 0.913
20		4.0 \pm 0.832	2.1 \pm 0.862	56.8 \pm 0.881
30		3.9 \pm 0.771	2.4 \pm 0.811	61.2 \pm 0.682
50		3.8 \pm 0.683	2.6 \pm 0.613	69.2 \pm 0.813
70		4.1 \pm 0.613	2.3 \pm 0.832	63.2 \pm 0.913
100		4.3 \pm 0.991	2.0 \pm 0.618	54.2 \pm 0.811
120		4.4 \pm 0.661	1.9 \pm 0.913	44.6 \pm 0.683
CaCO ₃		00	3.8 \pm 0.981	2.6 \pm 0.991
	500	6.2 \pm 0.591	2.7 \pm 0.861	48.3 \pm 0.713
	100	6.4 \pm 0.661	3.2 \pm 0.791	33.2 \pm 0.831
	150	6.2 \pm 0.826	2.8 \pm 0.811	22.1 \pm 0.681
	200	6.0 \pm 0.613	2.3 \pm 0.711	16.1 \pm 0.663

because the pH changed more alkaline side which was proved to be inhibitory to fungal growth and little or more solubilization of phosphate in the medium of such high pH as supported by other workers^{20,21}. Also calcium carbonate might interact with the phosphate release and subsequently inhibiting the solubilization process.

Effect of trace elements:

Iron requirement for *Aspergillus niger* AB100 was furnished by adding FeSO₄.7H₂O (1–30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in the medium. It was observed that maximum solubilization took place at 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of FeSO₄.7H₂O. Zinc sulphate as a source of Zn²⁺ caused negligible growth of the fungus at higher concentrations and solubilization of phosphate was greatly inhibited. The final pH of the medium was also increased, thus resulting in poor phosphate availability. Higher concentrations of this metal ion often proved to be toxic and led to mutagenic changes in microorganisms⁷. It was observed that the growth medium which supplied with copper (added as CuSO₄.5H₂O at concentrations ranging from 1.0 to 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), supported minute growth of *Aspergillus niger* AB100 at 1.0 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ but inhibited at higher concentrations. It was due to toxicity of

copper at higher concentrations. Manganese supplied to the medium as MnSO₄.H₂O aided fungal growth but higher concentrations did not increase the mycelia dry weight. However phosphate solubilization was not supported and increased in concentrations caused a decreased in phosphate solubilization. Manganese though supported growth of the fungus, inhibited the biosynthesis of the same primary and secondary metabolites as supported by other workers²³. The requirement of nickel for fungal growth is well known. Nickel ion (added as NiSO₄.6H₂O) when added in graded amounts the increased growth of the fungus did not enhance solubilization. Cobalt was essential for the synthesis of vitamin B₁₂ and though it supported the growth of the fungus but did not cause an increase in the yield of the solubilization process. Molybdenum was also essential for nitrogen metabolism especially when grown on nitrate containing medium. For our experiment, it was observed that molybdenum salt when added in graded amounts caused adequate growth of the fungus but did not enhance phosphate solubilization. It was observed that vanadium ion when supplied to the medium as NH₄VO₃ caused appreciable growth of the fungus but did

Fig. 1. Effects of trace elements on final pH of the growth medium after solubilization of phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100 (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n=6).

Fig. 2. Effects of trace elements on cellular growth of *Aspergillus niger* AB100 during solubilization of phosphate (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n=6).

Fig. 3. Effects of trace elements on cellular growth after solubilization of phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100 (Values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where n=6).

not enhance solubilization. The overall effects of the trace elements on pH of the broth, fungal growth and solubilization of rock phosphate have been summarized in Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively.

Conclusion

Among the macro elements examined, KCl and KH_2PO_4 showed the positive effect on solubilization of phosphate from rock phosphate at concentration of 70 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

respectively but calcium ion had adverse effect on solubilization of phosphate. It has been found that, among the micro elements studied, Fe^{2+} , 20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ showed positive effect on solubilization of phosphate from rock phosphate. Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Mo^{6+} had no significant effect on phosphorus solubilization but Cu^{2+} and Zn^{2+} exhibited adverse effect on phosphorous solubilization for rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100.

After optimization of different macro and micro mineral elements in the synthetic broth, solubilization of phosphorous in terms of P_2O_5 was increased significantly ($p < 0.001$) from 35.95 to 65.05%. Alteration of final pH in the broth also showed significant ($p < 0.05$) alteration towards acidity. Dry cell weight also exhibited significant increase ($p < 0.001$) from 0.95 to 3.56 mg/ml.

Thus, it can be concluded that, optimization of different mineral elements led to overall improvement in the solubilization of rock phosphate by *Aspergillus niger* AB100.

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